

Incorporation of **Agent-Based Modelling** for **Archaeologists** into a digital **archaeological skills passport**

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Year Published: 2024

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

Background

The Agent Based Modelling for Archaeologists (ABMA) project was an international collaboration co-funded by the Erasmus+ Programme of the European Union (2021-2-IE01-KA220-VET-000049054). The collaboration involved Aarhus University, Leiden University, Landward Research, and Saxion University of Applied Sciences. The goal of this project was to create Open Educational Resources (OERs) and accompanying materials where participants learn to create simulations using Agent-Based Modeling. This project is coordinated by Landward Research.

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As part of the project we integrated the OER learning objectives into an archaeological skills passport.

What is an archaeological skills passport?

An archaeological skills passport is a tool for tracking and verifying the archaeological skills that an individual has. The first passport was created as part of *The Ardnamurchan Transitions Project*, a long running investigation of the archaeology and history of the Ardnamurchan Peninsula, Western Scotland, run by the Universities of Leicester and Manchester, with Archaeology Scotland¹. Since then the passport has spread around the world to countries such as Germany² and the United States.

While there are many different versions, in its simplest form it is a log booklet listing skills that others can verify by signing off on their level of competencies.

What is a digital skills passport?

This is the same concept as a physical skills passport but in digitised to overcome some of the drawbacks of a physical skills passport:

- losing a copy means losing a record;
- inability to easily share the log;
- costs of production;
- ability to verify those signing off on skill levels.

¹ Cobb, H., and K. Croucher, 'Pedagogy, Political Economy, and Training', *Assembling Archaeology: Teaching, Practice, and Research* (Oxford, 2020; online edn, Oxford Academic, 20 Aug. 2020), <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780198784258.003.0004>.

² Karl, R., Möller, K., et al. 2020 The Archaeology Skills Passport: A means to record archaeological skills acquired through practice, *Archäologische Informationen*, Volume 42, p. 237-249 <https://doi.org/10.11588/ai.2019.0.69362>.

Integration

A trans-Atlantic consortium has been established to create a digital archaeological skills passport. It consists of the professional body in the United States of America, the *Register of Professional Archaeologists* and five archaeological companies in Europe, working and based in Ireland, the United Kingdom, the Netherlands, Germany and France. This is the passport that the ABMA aspired to integrate with OERs created as part of our project.

Members of the ABMA project team met with members of the Digital Skills Passport Team four times over the course of 2022, 2023 and 2024. Three of those meetings were remote meetings via Teams and Zoom. The last meeting was an in-person to sign off on the work. The results of these meetings was a decision on how ABM skills could be incorporated into the Digital Skills Passport.

Agent Based Modelling (ABM) will be placed within the transferable skills category of the Archaeological Skills Passport. This will be facilitated by the creation of a larger category of Analytical Skills and then a sub-category of modelling. ABM will sit within that category, modelling. Within ABM there are two top level categories - creation of models (with two sub-categories) and analysis of the results.

The following table presents the high level skills in the digital skills passport (excluding sub-categories for brevity), and then showing the fuller breakdown of the proposed new skills:

- 1 Handtools
- 2 Recording
- 3 Site Photography
- 4 Planning
- 5 Drawing
- 6 Collection of Samples
- 7 Artefact Recovery, Recording & Storage
- 8 Site Safety
- 9 Survey
- 10 Geophysics
- 11 Landscape/Field Walking Survey
- 12 Environmental Processing
- 13 Finds Processing
- 14 GIS & Data Management
- 15 Data Entry/Archiving
- 16 Excavation of human remains
- 17 Report and Article Writing
- 18 Illustration and Graphics
- 19 Public Outreach

- 20 Aerial photographs
 - 21 Interpreting maps
 - 22 Consulting grey literature
 - 23 Writing desk-based assessments
 - 24 Writing project specifications & designs
 - 25 Documentary research to enhance existing records
 - 26 Communication
 - 27 Financial management
 - 28 Life skills/personal & social care
 - 29 Literacy
 - 30 Numeracy
 - 31 Patience/accuracy
 - 32 Problem solving
 - 33 Research skills
 - 34 Responsibility/leadership
 - 35 Self-motivation
 - 36 Teamwork
 - 37 Time management
 - 38 Analytical Skills
 - 38.1 Modelling
 - 38.1.1 Computational Modelling
 - 38.1.1.1 Agent Based Modelling
 - 38.1.1.1.1 Software mastery
 - 38.1.1.1.1.1 Creation of models and understanding of key components
 - 38.1.1.1.1.2 Integration of other fields - GIS, network science
 - 38.1.1.1.2 Analysis and interpretation of results
 - 38.1.2 Mathematical Modelling
- etc.

Current Incorporation

At the end of the ABMA project (March 2024) the digital skills passport has not yet been published. However, it should occur soon (within the course of 2024) and will be found at this url: <https://archaeologypassport.com>.